

THE ROLE OF YOUTH IN CREATING A PERFECT SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of youth in creating an energetic society based on the idea of a free and prosperous life in the new Uzbekistan and uniting them in the heart. Practical efficiency and the interests of the people are the main goals of social reform. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and take it to a new level.

Introduction

What a beautiful and flawless season of human life, a time of great dreams and unique opportunities. Youth is a dream. This is confidence. It is a quest for courage. This is lyricism and romance. This is the beginning of grand plans for the future and independence. Improving the political, legal and educational knowledge of young people should be raised to the level of public policy. In this regard, the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the regions, interdepartmental councils on youth issues headed by authorities, the Commission on Youth Affairs in the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and the Youth Club. New kindergartens, schools, universities, branches of prestigious foreign universities, cultural and sports facilities, "Temurbek School", "Presidential Schools", "Schools of Creativity" are being established in our country, facilities serve to nurture a new generation of mature professionals who are competitive in today's globalized environment. Today, the role of youth in building an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan is invaluable. If you count the opportunities that are being created for young people, morning and night will be connected, but you will not be able to enumerate them. No matter what area you look at, it is on the path to development, growth and development. All these are the wide-ranging, topical and, of course, highly productive conditions and opportunities provided by the head of our state to the youth. There is a deep meaning in the beginning of the hadis of the great Imam Bukhari, Al-Jame as-Sahih, which says, "All good deeds depend on intention, and everyone is given only what he intends." A nation with a great purpose will have a great job, a bright life and a prosperous future. To date, the Youth is Our Future Fund has allocated 692.4 billion soums in soft loans for business projects of our young people, creating about 25,000 new jobs in the country. This will be especially evident when the "Youth Labor Guzar" and 19 "Young Entrepreneurs" co-working centers are commissioned. Patriotic, dedicated to the motherland

of our people, the Order of Friendship and the Medal of Fame, the State Prize named after Zulfiya, the Medal of the Builder of the Future, the Badge of the Badge of Uzbekistan, the Prize of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan was awarded with. Nodirbek Abdusattorov, who won the World Rapid Chess Championship yesterday, was awarded the state prize "Brave Boy" by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on youth, science, education, health, culture and sports. Adviser on Abdusattorovich. I don't think anything can introduce the country to the world apart from sports quickly. There are many such achievements. Such leadership of young people in the fields of science, culture, arts, sports, reading, does not leave anyone indifferent. Wouldn't you say Science Olympiads ?! At the International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO), International Physics Olympiad (IPHO), International Chemistry Olympiad (ICHO) and International Biology Olympiad (IBO), Uzbek youth won a total of 10 medals. Of these, 3 are gold, 2 are silver and 5 are bronze. These results are recorded for the first time in the history of independent Uzbekistan. The real backbone of Uzbekistan is such educated and aspiring young people. Another great opportunity for our youth. The El-Yurt Umidi Foundation provides 420 places for young people to study at prestigious universities and research centers of foreign countries in the 2022-2023 academic year (120 bachelors; 180 masters and 120 doctoral students). announced an open scholarship competition. Not all educated and talented young people can afford to study abroad, let alone study at a prestigious higher education institution. This is a great opportunity for such young people to realize their dreams and get a quality education abroad, says the director of the Youth Affairs Agency.

To create an enlightened society, first of all, educated young people are needed. And in order to prepare an educated generation for the future, it is always necessary to read a book. As the head of state said: "A child who reads one book today, can control ten children who watch TV tomorrow." This is the fourth of five important initiatives proposed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019. Systematic work has been done to raise the morale of young people, to promote reading among them and this is being done to this day. In particular, it is important that the literature in the series "Youth Library" is distributed free of charge to all schools in the country and to the local councils of the Youth Union. One bright example is the Young Reader contest, which brings together educated young people between the ages of 10 and 30. If you have noticed, during Alisher Sadullayev's open dialogue with young people, he made a presentation on the systems, projects launched for young people this year and the opportunities that are expected to be realized for young people in the future.

Conclusion. I would like to conclude my article as follows.

Life goes on...

Minutes...

Hours...

Days...

Months...

Even, the years...

The wheel of life continues to rotate in this way. It doesn't matter who leaves or who comes, your problems, your laughter or your pain, your hard work or your inaction! Whether you are dreaming, standing up, or simply motionless, it will continue. Do you ever ask yourself what

I'm doing right now? What about before you go to bed at night?! What about gaining or losing something during the day?! Ever wondered?! What about your goals?! It's not about dreams, it's about your goals and goals! Are you worried that you won't be able to find the time you're wasting tomorrow?! Time is like a one-way train relay. It can't be pushed back or taken out of control! By the time it stops, life will have stopped! Just think about the present, what you can do now, and what you can achieve tomorrow! Don't sleep, wake up! Don't sit still, read. Don't run! Just don't want to, just get it! Embrace all of your goals and achieve them. Most importantly, believe sincerely! You can do it! Tomorrow?! Never say early! Live in the moments! Remember, life goes on. And you only have the results left. Together for a great future!

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